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PROJECT REPORT

'Others' and Consociational Democracy.

Citizens, Civil Society, and Politics
in South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina.

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Citizens, Civil Society, and Politics in South Tyrol and
Bosnia Herzegovina.

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List of abbreviations

ASt - Autonomy Statute

BiH - Bosnia Herzegovina

BL - Banja Luka

BR - Brunico/Bruneck

BZ - Bolzano/Bozen

DF - *Demokratska Fronta*, Democratic Front

DPA - Dayton Peace Agreement

FBiH - Federation of Bosnia Herzegovina

ME - Merano/Meran

MO - Mostar

NS - *Naša Stranka*, Our Party

PD - *Democratic Party*

RS - Republika Srpska

SDP - *Socijaldemokratska Partija Bosne i Hercegovine*, Social Democratic Party of Bosnia Herzegovina

SNSD - *Savez nezavisnih socijaldemokrata*, Alliance of Independent Social Democrats

SRJ - Sarajevo

ST - South Tyrol

SVP - *Südtiroler Volkspartei*, South Tyrolean People's Party

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1 - Introduction

Arendt Lijphart defined plural societies as societies clearly divided along religious, ideological, linguistic, cultural, or ethnic lines into separate sub-societies with their own political parties, groups of interest and media (Lijphart 1977). Consociational arrangements build upon the fundamental assumption that 'it is more perverse to deny the existence and salience of ethnic identities [...] than it is to build upon them' (O'Leary 2005: 19), hence they envisage a model of power-sharing based on four main elements: 1) a coalition government made up of political leaders representing all significant groups; 2) proportional representation of these groups in state institutions; 3) veto rights; and 4) a high degree of autonomy, sometimes reflected in a decentralised state system and/or federalism. There are, however, two main types of consociations according to how the groups that will share power are identified: corporate consociations identify groups according to ascriptive criteria such as language, religion, ethnicity; liberal consociations, instead, reward any political identity emerging in democratic elections according to the logic of self-determination (McCulloch 2013). Consociational arrangements are often implemented in plural realities, also and especially as tools of post-conflict resolution; among others, consociational power-sharing mechanisms have been implemented in Lebanon, Iraq, Cyprus, Northern Ireland, Macedonia, Kosovo, as well as in Bosnia Herzegovina and South Tyrol - the latter two being the case studies of this project.

Consociations, and particularly corporate ones, have been widely criticised (Brass 1991; Horowitz 1985; Noel 2005; Reilly 2004) and accused of leading to ethnic political pluralism - where political parties tend to strengthen ethnic rather than civic identities; provoking immobilism; institutionally privileging collective identities at the expense of more emancipated forms of self-identification (Brubaker, Cooper 2001; O'Leary 2005); cementing boundaries between the various communities, and ultimately undermining dialogue, compromise, and integration. Additionally, consociations have been accused of discriminating against those bearers of identities not envisaged by the system, excluding them: in fact, not every citizen of a plural society can or wants to identify with the ethno-divisions (Agarin et al 2018), and the so-called 'Others' constitute a heterogeneous group, whose members are not explicitly included in the consociational system and mechanisms. In the light of corporate consociations' ethnic connotation, these citizens inevitably face a number of obstacles - both formal, e.g. concerning the mechanisms of redistribution of resources based on 'ethnic quota' systems, and informal, e.g. concerning the groups' socio-economic status and prestige.

This project focuses its attention on these potentially excluded citizens, the 'Others', and it does so by looking at the corporate consociations of South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina - the former build upon the ethno-linguistic groups of Italian, German and Ladin speakers; while the latter are grounded upon the Constituent Peoples of Bosniaks, Bosnian Serbs and Bosnian Croats. The research carries out a multi-level analysis accounting for the perspectives of ordinary citizens; the political and institutional world; and the civil society sector understood as a potential intermediary between the other two levels. The project's main aims are:

- i) to shed light on how 'Others' navigate the ethnic divide and governance - whether adapting or reacting to it;
- ii) to understand to what extent consociations succeed or fail in representing and including 'Others', accommodating and satisfying their needs and interests; and
- iii) in the light of increased socio-demographic changes and heterogeneity, to have a clearer picture of what possible future developments there are for consociation.

1.1 Case Studies

The case studies selected for this project are the corporate consociations of South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina. South Tyrol, the northernmost Italian province, is populated by two major ethno-linguistic groups: German (69,41%) and Italian (26,06%) ones; and by a third, smaller, group of Ladin

speakers (4,53%)¹. The German speakers have traditionally lived in the more rural areas, while the Italian speakers mostly in the urban centres - especially in Bolzano/Bozen, and along the border with Trentino. The Ladins, instead, are mostly concentrated in the Badia and Gardena valleys. BiH, instead, is mostly populated by three major ethnic groups: Bosniaks (50,01%), Bosnian Croats (15,5%) and Bosnian Serbs (30,08%)² - the latter almost exclusively inhabiting the Entity of Republika Srpska, while the other two groups mostly living in the Entity called Federation of Bosnia Herzegovina (FBiH)³. In Bosnia Herzegovina, the non-ethnically aligned citizens ('Others') account for 3,7% of the total population, while in South Tyrol those who declare 'Other' and then aggregate to one of the three groups represent 1,68% (see Tables).

In the light of ST's and BiH's ethno-territorial composition, data have been collected in the cities of Bolzano/Bozen, Merano/Meran, Brunico/Bruneck in South Tyrol; and in Sarajevo, Mostar and Banja Luka in Bosnia Herzegovina. South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina are two highly dissimilar contexts (with Dayton's Bosnia probably being the most unsuccessful example of consociationalism, while South Tyrol is perhaps the most efficient one). Additionally, issues concerning ethnic identity and belonging as well as the issue of 'Others' were and remain of fundamental importance from both a social and political perspective, as well as in the academic debate, hence making the comparison scientifically relevant.

Tab 1 - Population by ethnic / national affiliation - Municipality and Entity level - Bosnia Herzegovina (based on declarations made during the Population Census 2013)

	Bosniaks	Bosnian Croats	Bosnian Serbs	Others
Sarajevo	80,74%	4,94%	3,78%	10,54%
Mostar	46,75%	51,21%	4,42%	3,40%
Banja Luka	5,45%	3,02%	87,21%	1,02%
Entity FBiH	70,4%	22,44%	2,50%	4,6%
Entity RS	14,00%	2,41%	81,51%	2,1%
Brčko district	42,40%	20,07%	34,06%	2,4%

Source: Census of population, households and dwellings in Bosnia and Herzegovina - 2013 Final results (<http://www.statistika.ba/#link2>)

Tab 2 - Percentage composition of the three official language groups - South Tyrol (based on declarations made during the Population Census 2011) by municipality

	Italian speakers	German speakers	Ladin speakers
Bolzano/Bozen	73.80 %	25.52 %	0.68 %
Merano/Meran	49.06 %	50.47 %	0.47 %
Brunico/Bruneck	15.24 %	82.47 %	2.29 %

Source: Provincial Statistic Institute 2019. *South Tyrol in Figures 2019*, p. 16-17

¹ Population Census 2011. <https://astat.provincia.bz.it/it/censimento-generale-popolazione-abitazioni.asp>

² Census of population, households and dwellings in Bosnia and Herzegovina - 2013 Final results. <http://www.statistika.ba/#link2>

³ BiH is one single country yet internally partitioned into two Entities: the Federation of BiH comprises 51% of the Bosnian territory, while the Republika Srpska occupies 49%. Additionally, the District of Brčko became autonomous in 1999, and does not belong to any Entity;

Tab 3 - Language group declaration and aggregation - South Tyrol, Population Census 2011

	Declaration of belonging	Declaration of aggregation
Italian	97,49%	2,51%
German	98,65%	1,350%
Ladin	97,95%	2,05%
Total	98,32%	1,68%

Source: ASTAT Istituto Provinciale di Statistica 06/2012. *Censimento della Popolazione 2011. Determinazione della consistenza dei tre gruppi linguistici della Provincia Autonoma di Bolzano-Alto Adige*, n. 38, p. 4

1.2 Research Questions

In order to explore how citizens, politics and civil society frame and tackle the issue of 'Others' - their inclusion and representation within consociational systems, the questions driving the research are the following:

i) How do citizens 'Others' deal with an ethnically connoted and organised society and state?

- What mechanisms and strategies do 'Others' adopt in order to become part of the system?

- How do they interact with ethnically connoted institutions? What obstacles do they face, and how do they overcome them? When, and if, making 'identity choices', which group do Others opt for? and for what reasons?

ii) How does the world of politics address the issue of 'Others' ?

- Which political parties seek to represent 'Others' citizens? How do they address, and overcome, the limits and potential exclusion intrinsic to consociationalism?

- How do consociational mechanisms and institutions account for, respond to, and successfully accommodate the needs of citizens 'Others' ?

iii) What role does civil society play?

- How do civil society organisations address the issue of 'Others'? What, if any, are the initiatives proposed and the channels used to achieve greater inclusion and representation?

- What kinds of interaction and cooperation, if any, exist between and among civil society, actors, the world of politics, and citizens 'Others'?

1.3 Hypotheses

The question of 'Others' being very delicate from several points of view (political-institutional, constitutional, social, individual-personal), it is assumed that:

Hp 1) 'Others' are more inclined to adapt to the system when it comes to interactions with institutions and politics, while they are more resistant (reluctant?) when it comes to their social lives;

Hp 2) 'Others' coming from mixed unions between domestic groups adapt to the system by adopting the most convenient collective identity in terms of social prestige and political-institutional representation; we thus expect rare, or no, interaction with the civil society organisations that aim to create greater inclusion and representation within the existing system;

Hp 3) 'Others' coming from mixed unions/marriages between a domestic and a foreign group, as well as foreigners either possessing state citizenship or a long stay residence permit, attribute different meanings to the existing institutional divisions. We thus expect them to more consistently seek greater inclusion and representation, hence to interact with both political parties and civil society.

In the detail of each case study, it is assumed that:

Hp 5) the corruption and ethno-nationalism characterising the Bosnian Herzegovinian political landscape discourage civil society from cooperating with (most of) the political parties - for the largest part nationalist and ethnically exclusive; while, instead, they encourage fruitful interactions with the citizens. On the contrary, the more moderate character of the South Tyrolean political parties make them a potential interlocutor of civil society - in turn, expected to play a mediating role between the citizens and their politicians, hence to interact and cooperate with both of them;

Hp 6) due to historical and conflict-related reasons, we expect civil society and non-ethnic political parties in ST to address the issue of 'Others' by foreseeing moving beyond ethnic divisions - which means to either move from corporate to liberal consociationalism or the progressive abandonment of ethnic power-sharing mechanisms. On the contrary, in BiH we expect the social and political actors to be aware of the impossibility of abandoning ethnic categories, hence aiming for recognition of 'Others' as Constituent People;

Hp 7) however, due to reasons of stability, we expect to observe in both consociations a generalised lack of political will to tackle and 'solve' the issue of 'Others' so that, on the one hand, citizens potentially Others are incentivised to adapt to the ethnic governance and divide; while, on the other, civil society's role shrinks and the influencing potential of non-ethnic parties diminishes.

1.4 Research Methodology

The methodology used in carrying out the project is qualitative, and the arguments presented have been built upon first-hand empirical material. After an initial phase of bibliographic research (6 months), a longer phase of data collection (12 months) followed. The fieldwork in South Tyrol (September 2019 to March 2020) took place in the cities of Bolzano/Bozen, Merano/Meran and Brunico/Bruneck. Semi-structured interviews were performed both in person and via telephone. Data collection in Bosnia Herzegovina, instead, began in late August 2020 and, due to the spread of COVID-19, could not take place physically. Yet, thanks to the use of online communication platforms (Skype and Viber), the interviews with the respondents from the Bosnian cities of Sarajevo, Mostar, and Banja Luka were successfully conducted, without compromising either the quality of the data gathered or the project's overall success. The interview respondents were reached through the snowball sampling technique; they were individuals of all genders, aged between 20 and 60 and, in order to avoid 'methodological nationalism' and 'ethnic labelling', they were not approached according to their potential ethno-linguistic origins (which, when it did emerge, was only during our conversations). A total number of 60 interviews were performed in the territory of South Tyrol, while about 45 in that of Bosnia Herzegovina. The interviews lasted about 1 hour each, and were carried out in Italian language in ST, while in English in BiH. When possible and allowed by the interlocutors, the conversations were recorded - though in accordance with current privacy legislation, all the personal data and information provided remain anonymous.

In order to provide as truthful an overview as possible of the topic analysed, the project investigated the question of 'Others' from different perspectives, hence the final sample included: i) ordinary citizens; ii) individuals belonging to the political and institutional world; and iii) individuals active in

local civil society organisations.

The questions asked, adapted according to the interlocutor, explored three main macro-areas:

'Others' and institutions: the goal was to investigate which obstacles and institutional discriminations people who are bearers of identities 'not included and not foreseen' by the consociational system are likely to face; which strategies might possibly be adopted to circumvent/overcome those obstacles; and which criteria inform the 'identity choices' made in order to enter the system;

'Others' and political representation: the aim was to assess how citizens, and particularly those potentially 'Others', interact with the world of politics; which political alternatives are committed to representing and including 'Others'; and how these parties tackle the issue of 'Others' - proposing solutions aimed to guarantee greater/beyond ethnic inclusion and representation;

The future of consociational societies: the interviews also sought to understand whether and how, according to the various social and political actors questioned, changes in the ethno-cultural composition of the social fabric are, or are not, bringing about a structural change consisting of more inclusive institutions and political representatives - hence addressing the paramount question of how plural societies grounded upon corporate consociationalism might evolve.

1.5 Scientific Relevance

Because of the methodology used and the small size of the sample, the research results presented have no statistical relevance and cannot be generalised to the whole South Tyrolean and Bosnian Herzegovinian populations. Nonetheless, the study represents an innovative contribution to the scientific literature in the fields of social and political sciences, as it furthers the debate on group inclusion in divided societies grounded upon consociational mechanisms by i) combining a structural analysis with first-hand qualitative data; and ii) focusing the attention on the often 'neglected' 'Others'. Last but not least, such a comparative work sheds light on similar dynamics existing in apparently very different contexts; it furnishes important information about how, and to what extent, the social and political actors composing the plural society frame, address or neglect the issue of inclusion/exclusion of 'Others'; finally, it provides interested scholars and policy makers with the tools needed for re-thinking, or ameliorating, the consociational mechanisms themselves.

1.6 Structure of the Report

The report is structured as follows: **Chapter 2** familiarises the reader with the consociational system, its mechanisms and principles, also introducing the debate concerning the formal exclusion of 'Others'. **Chapters 3, 4, and 5** use the empirical material collected in the years 2019 - 2020 to explore and reconstruct the Others issue in the cases of South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina. Each chapter looks at the topic surveyed from different perspectives - that of ordinary citizens, that of the political-institutional world, and that of civil society - so as to highlight dynamics and synergies between actors and factors. **Chapter 6** then focuses on the territorial dimension and looks at the similarities and differences that emerged between the South Tyrolean cities of Bolzano/Bozen, Merano/Meran, and Brunico/Bruneck, and the Bosnian Herzegovinian cities of Sarajevo, Mostar, and Banja Luka. **Chapter 7** explores the theme of the future of plural and consociational societies, while the **Conclusion** sums up the findings and, by building upon the notion of 'opportunistic alignment', proposes a reflection concerning the broader theme of consociationalism - its apparent rigidity and factual flexibility.

2 - Others in Consociations

2.1 The South Tyrolean 'Complex Power-Sharing'

The South Tyrolean 'complex power-sharing' (Wolff 2008: 330) protects the linguistic minorities through the implementation of a set of mechanisms, one of which is the ethnic quota system. Introduced back in 1946 with the Gruber - De Gasperi Agreement, the principles of corporate consociationalism were retained with the entering into force (1972) of the so-called Second – and current – Autonomy Statute (ASt). The ASt was, indeed, grounded upon the 'separation and forced cooperation of the two main linguistic groups, German speakers and Italians' (Alber, Palermo 2012: 293) while special rules were provided for the third group, the Ladin speakers. Consociational mechanisms were essentially meant to include, represent, and safeguard each group's identity, culture, and interest, while assuring and maintaining the ethno-linguistic plurality of the public bodies and institutions of the state. The tool identified to achieve such a goal was the ethnic quota system - which applies 'to everyday life and the whole public sphere, and establish[es] a detailed regime of individual and collective linguistic rights (Alber 2021: 187). Ethnic proportions are calculated on the basis of the most recent census and are applied according to the ethno-linguistic groups' numerical strength. The tool used to identify quota size is the so-called 'linguistic declaration or aggregation'. By asking all citizens aged 18 or above living in the ST territory to self-identify/aggregate themselves with one of the three ethno-linguistic groups (Italian, German, Ladin), the declaration allows the size of each group to be determined and, in a second step, the ethnic quota proportions to be calculated, to which a set of rights and benefits are connected. From a citizen's perspective, the declaration allows a person 1) to 'stand for public office; 2) to be entitled to file an application to receive subsidies and [...] 3) to be employed as a civil servant' (Alber 2021: 190).

Although functional to its aim, this system based on ethnic proportionality is not perfect: all those bearers of 'non standard and not foreseen identities' are (theoretically) cut out from the system. The issue was initially raised, in the 1980s, by Alexander Langer⁴, a politician and member of the Greens (*Verdi-Grüne-Vërc*), forbidden to run for mayor of Bolzano/Bozen because he refused to provide the linguistic declaration during the 1991 census. While citizens had been given (in 1991) the possibility to declare themselves 'Others', they are nonetheless compelled to 'aggregate' with one of the three ethno-linguistic groups if they want to actively participate in the political life of their society, as well as take advantage of the benefits, rights, and resources redistributed according to ethnic criteria. Moreover, although a 'less discriminating' system was achieved following the 2005 reform of the by-law to the statute⁵, failing/refusing to provide the linguistic declaration or aggregate to one of the ethno-linguistic groups, automatically leads to exclusion from the proportional system and the waiving of the rights and benefits enjoyable only through it. And while citizens are allowed to modify their linguistic declaration at any time, the changes only come into effect 18 months later. From an institutional perspective, therefore, the individual right of freedom of self-identification and identity expression is limited – and may even be disadvantageous – for the sake of protecting collectivity and the system's smooth functioning (Lantschner, Poggeschi 2008). Further evidence in this direction is the fact that the declaration of linguistic belonging is free and does not have to correspond to 'reality', and there are no checks, sanctions, or punishments impeding one from making 'false declarations' for opportunistic reasons.

⁴ Alexander Langer, citizen of Bolzano/Bozen politically active in the Greens, questioned the ST's ethnic power-sharing mechanisms - accused, as he used to say, of trapping people into ethnic cages;

⁵ the reform separated the census - anonymous and used for statistical purposes, from the declaration of linguistic belonging - on a voluntarily basis ever since then if someone wishes to benefit from the ethnic quota system;

2.2 The Tripartite System of Bosnia Herzegovina

The Dayton Peace Agreement (DPA) signed in Dayton, Ohio, in 1995, ended the Bosnian war and laid the foundations for re-building the state. According to the new domestic constitution, the DPA's Annex IV, Bosnian Serbs, Bosnian Croats, and Bosniaks are 'Constituent Peoples' of BiH along with 'Others'. The latter represents an umbrella category including both members of the 17 minorities living in the Bosnian Herzegovinian territory since then, and all those who cannot or do not want to identify themselves with any of the main ethno-national groups.

In the light of its ethnic heterogeneity as well as its conflictual past, and in order to avoid the supremacy of one group over the others while guaranteeing their socio-economic equality and proportional representation, power-sharing mechanisms grounded upon both ethnic and ethno-territorial criteria have been implemented post-war. Ethnic quotas apply also in BiH - yet these are determined according to the data gathered during the 1991, pre-war, census of the population (still in place all over the country, except for Canton Sarajevo). The application of the so-called 'national key' (Pearson 2014) is however often based on informal rather than official criteria, yet these are carefully observed in all areas of social and political life even when and where not officially prescribed. Regarding 'Others', the DPA stipulates that, at the state level, these cannot (officially) run either for the tripartite state Presidency or for the House of Peoples. One member of the Cabinet, the Council of Ministers, can however be Other. At the municipal level, 'Others' always have a reserved quota. Overall, however, the Bosnian institutional and political systems remain ethnic and exclusive, and 'Others' on the very margin of public and political life of the country.

The institutional discrimination suffered by 'Others' has for long time been neglected, yet it was brought to light in 2008, when the representatives of the Jewish and Roma communities (Jacob Finci and Dervo Sejdić) sued the state of BiH because they were forbidden to run for the state tripartite Presidency in virtue of their being 'Others'. The European Court of Human Rights issued a judgement in 2009, which compelled the state of BiH to modify its constitution in a more inclusive direction. To the present day, an agreement still has to be achieved, and cases similar to the Sejdić-Finci one have multiplied - further highlighting the ethnic and ethno-territorial discriminations intrinsic to the very consociational mechanisms.

Nonetheless, it is worth saying that, although a tool similar to the South Tyrolean declaration of linguistic belonging is lacking, and the criteria determining one's own (alleged) group membership are shady and unofficial (generally based on assumptions deriving from people's personal and family names), the absence of checks and potential punishments also allows and incentivises 'Others' from BiH 'to lie' about their potential belonging, align with the ethnic divided and/or switch identity according to need.

2.3 Who are the 'Others'?

By definition, 'Others' are all those who cannot or do not want to identify with the available collective categories (Agarin et al 2018). The content of a category is highly heterogeneous, and its potential members are confronted with the choice of either aligning with the ethnic divide - if they want to be fully represented, enjoy rights and resources, and fully participate in their society's public life; or endorsing supra-ethnic forms of identification, challenging the ethnic governance, yet remaining outside the system, invisible to its eyes - hence refusing all those benefits, rights and resources redistributed according to ethnic criteria. According to the data collected, in today's South Tyrolean society, those who might potentially fall into the category 'Others' are:

- i) the *traditional linguistically mixed*⁶, coming from mixed unions/marriages between domestic linguistic groups;

- ii) the *new mixed*, coming from mixed unions/marriages between a domestic and a foreign group;
- iii) *new minorities*, foreigners living in ST either possessing Italian citizenship or a long stay residence permit equating them to Italian citizens;
- iv) *ethnic objectors*, individuals rejecting any ethno-linguistic affiliation. These sub-group members were definitely more visible and louder in the 1980s, while today they have disappeared.

In BiH, instead, while group boundaries and identities are sharply defined from a political-institutional point of view, life experiences, mixed marriage, territorially scattered family ties, anti-nationalist political opinions, as well as the impact of identity politics and war dynamics have concurred to make individuals' identities, feelings of attachment, and modalities of self-identification very difficult to define once and for all. Yet, if we are to put some order into the complexity of the catch-all 'Others' category, we might identify:

- i) *ethnic minorities*, Bosnian Herzegovinian citizens belonging to ethnic groups different from the three constituent peoples (i.e. Jews, Roma, etc.);
- v) the *in-between*, individuals coming from mixed unions/marriages between two or more Bosnian ethnic groups (corresponding to the South Tyrolean *traditional linguistically mixed*);
- vi) the *against*, all those avoiding and rejecting any form of ethno-national self-identification (corresponding to the South Tyrolean *ethnic objectors*). Among these, we might also include all those who have either retained or post-war endorsed non-aligned forms of identification (i.e. Yugoslav, Sarajevan, Bosnian Herzegovinian).

⁶ in South Tyrol these individuals are called 'mistilingue' in Italian - where the term has a neutral connotation; yet 'gemischtsprachig' in German - where the term is negatively connoted;

3 - How do Citizens 'Others' Interact with an Ethnically Connoted and Organised System?

3.1 Not only 'Linguistically Mixed'

While discussing how and through which channels citizens, and especially those potentially 'Others', interact with ethnic state institutions, the numerous interviews performed in South Tyrol made clear that i) virtually everybody, 'Others' included, aligns with the ethnic divide and governance; and ii) the criterion generally driving the choice is rooted in opportunism. *There are no 'heart issues', it is all about opportunism [...] The only thing that matters is work and the opportunities connected to the declaration. Money is the only thing that matters here* (Male, BZ, Nov 2019).

South Tyrol is a small territory in which a set of favourable conditions allowed for economic growth and generalised socio-economic prosperity. Although there are no disparities between the groups, those potentially 'Others' generally align with the most convenient collective identity in terms of socio-economic prestige. As a young woman stated: *I did not know what to choose because I grew up bilingual and I come from a mixed family, but eventually I chose German because, in case of need, I will have many more chances to work in the public administration* (Female, ME, Jan 2020). Behavioural compliance with the ethnic governance - here addressed in terms of 'opportunistic alignment' - emerged to be the optimal strategy adopted by most if not all those potentially 'Others' in order to face, and successfully overcome, the obstacles intrinsic to corporate consociationalism.

As it emerged, not only those coming from mixed backgrounds, but foreigners living in ST too seem to conform for opportunistic reasons: *the same goes for the many women from Eastern Europe, coming from the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Moldova, and working in care homes for the elderly. They declare themselves as Ladins. I know many of them personally, and it would be stupid not to do that.* (Male, BZ, Sept 2019). While the 'identity choice' of 'Others' is influenced, among other things, by the amount of ethnic quotas reserved to each group, and that these vary across the territory, it is also true that the German group represents the 'winning' one - the one guaranteeing a higher number of chances⁷. Curiously enough, in fact, sometimes also the members of both the Italian and Ladin groups 'switch identities' for opportunistic reasons. As a (Italian) woman stated: *I did not want to be the vice-director of anyone, I wanted to be the director* (Female, BZ, Nov 2019)⁸. While another respondent explained that: *My husband is from Naples, he learnt German and appreciates the German culture, and yes - he declared himself as German. I don't understand where the problem is, why an Italian person cannot do that too. Eventually, what does 'linguistically mixed/mistilingue' mean? [...] I believe the declaration has been misunderstood, it is not an excluding mechanism, quite the opposite* (Female, ME, Dic 2019). And again, as a young woman confessed: *when I was 18, I declared myself as Ladin, but today I am not sure I would do the same, I would think differently. Because I am from the Val Badia, I have been told to say I am Ladin in order to have better job opportunities, to work in the public administration*⁹ (Female, BR, Jan 2020).

⁷ given that ethnic quotas are calculated according to the groups' numerical strength, the fact that the German speaking group is the largest in ST automatically implies its greater - though proportional - representation;

⁸ Italian speakers' 'uneasiness' (Carlà 2018) is rooted in the ASt itself, as due to its provisions the Italian group lost its dominant position especially but not solely in the economy sector. The Italian community's fear of being 'surpassed' by the German group has been statistically documented (ASTAT 2015, *Barometro linguistico dell'Alto Adige. Uso della lingua e identità linguistica in provincia di Bolzano*);

⁹ the Province of Bolzano/Bozen has a very sizeable public administration: out of 49,406 public employees, 41,949 are employees of the provincial administration (Provincial Statistics Institute 2019, *South Tyrol in figures 2019*);

The abundance of resources, equality among the groups, and smooth institutional functioning emerged as the key reasons why *anyone's* opportunistic alignment - the occasional identity shifting of domestic groups included - has become a reasonable and tolerable, highly practised, behavioural choice. Non-alignment, meaning either challenging ethnic proportionality, or refusing to declare/aggregate to one of the ethno-linguistic categories, has been described as an unreasonable choice, a decision that pragmatically leads to disadvantages. *Not declaring is clearly disadvantageous; and so it is if you fill out your declaration later, after your 18th birthday. Your rights are delayed and, for example, you won't benefit from the housing contribution which is up to 60.000€* (Female, BZ, Oct 2019).

Concerning the very mechanisms and tools regulating the Autonomous Province, the vast majority, if not all, of the respondents described the 'ethnic proportional system' as obsolete and anachronistic, and the declaration of linguistic belonging/aggregation as a very biased tool. *Statistics are biased because they do not account for Others, these people are not counted during the census. The percentages of those declaring themselves as Italian or German are biased too because they also include all the foreigners declaring as such for opportunism. Everybody is aware of the fact that this system is old and not keeping pace with the social changes, but changing it is risky. Who on earth would consciously waive all those guaranteed benefits and privileges?* (Male, BR, Feb 2020).

Nevertheless, the system's undoubted success in providing socio-economic security and living conditions above the national standard represent a good enough incentive not to question and challenge, hence dismantle and abandon, its mechanisms - though ethnic. As a young woman summarised: *You never know what is going to happen in the future [...] You must think wisely what group to aggregate with. There are reserved quotas and job positions - they told us about it at school. If one day I want to work in the public administration, I must be allowed to do so* (Female, BZ, Jan 2020)

3.2 Aligned and Non-Aligned

In BiH we can observe a slightly similar reality, as most people - 'Others' included - tend (when possible) to align with the ethnic divide without challenging its mechanisms and principles. The material collected in Sarajevo, Mostar, and Banja Luka revealed that, while on a personal level and in terms of everyday life interactions, ethnicity is not a matter of concern, it definitely is when it comes to the political and institutional spheres. Group membership, and by extension ethnic alignment, has been described as an indispensable tool to be deployed in order to enter the system, be represented and, more importantly, benefit from its (scarce) resources. The answers provided by the respondents from BiH however revealed a few major differences with the ST consociation:

i) the Bosnian state is a captured one, which means the public (and not only) institutions are controlled by the ruling ethno-national parties. It goes that, in order to enjoy and benefit from state resources and services, not only is membership of one of the recognised constituent people indispensable, but so are the 'connections' with either the ruling ethnic parties or members occupying key positions in the public administration. *Ethnicity first, then connections: always and in all cases, are both indispensable* (Female, MO, Oct 2020);

ii) accordingly, and contrary to ST, the implementation of ethnic quotas in BiH follows 'discretionary' criteria. More precisely, while the public authorities always make sure not to have '*ethnically pure sectors of the public administration*', ethnic quotas are not always formally prescribed and their implementation is often informal. As most respondents explained: *to make sure about your ethnicity, they will ask you to show your birth certificate - the only document displaying both your mother's and father's names and surnames. But when you apply for a public job, eventually, the only thing that works is connections: that is the guy winning the position. Nobody else.* (Male, SRJ, Nov 2020);

iii) contrary to what emerged in ST, in BiH there is no group enjoying a better/higher socio-economic status or prestige 'to side with'. Yet, as already mentioned, the lack of a tool similar to the South

Tyrolean declaration of linguistic belonging/aggregation, along with the absence of checks and potential punishments discouraging opportunistic behaviour, do allow for the opposite: *You can switch according to what is best for you. Many people do change their declared identity, constantly - according to the territory, the job, the seats...there are no rules, no punishments, nothing* (Male, Srj, Sept 2020). And again: *sometimes in order to apply for a public post, or to enter the power structure; sometimes because there are no seats for 'Others': people can declare they are...whatever* (Female, BL, Sept 2020);

iv) while the overall scenario points in the direction of ethnic and opportunistic alignment, mainly (but not only) due to a condition of state capture, it is worth mentioning that there exists a tiny but growing critical mass of people consciously rejecting ethnic labels while endorsing forms of self-identification not foreseen by the system (i.e. Bosnian Herzegovinian, Sarajevo). We might call these citizens 'non-aligned' or 'Others against'¹⁰ as their being 'Others' is a conscious choice, a reaction/rejection against the ethnic identity politicisation entrenched in consociationalism, promoted by the ethno-national political class, as well as the expression of the Bosnian and Yugoslav heritage of inclusiveness and cosmopolitanism;

v) last but not least, the respondents focused attention on the fact that there is one major exception to 'opportunistic alignment': those whose identities are somehow 'fixed'. As some explained: *those coming from ethnic minorities, such as the Roma, are actually the only ones really 'Others' and really discriminated: their identities are fixed, they cannot lie about it. If you are a Roma your identity is pretty clear, and you can't actually change it.* (Male, BL, Dic 2020). This not only confirms the already documented salience ethnic identity has in the Bosnian contexts but, more importantly, it focuses attention on a key difference with the ST system - which, by means of the declaration of linguistic belonging/aggregation has been able to include and allow literally *anybody* to participate in the proportional system, successfully implementing the ethnic quotas while avoiding informal and personalised relationships of favouritism.

Overall, however, the empirical material shows that, in both South Tyrol and Bosnian Herzegovina, to be and/or declare 'Other' is pragmatically disadvantageous and, whenever possible, citizens opt to conform and go along with the ethnic governance. Yet, while in BiH, the generalised and cross-ethnic economic difficulties, widespread corruption and clientelism in particular were the factors making 'opportunistic alignment' the optimal and most practised identity choice, in ST it was the exact opposite: cross-ethnic socio-economic wealth, the abundance of resources, and institutional smooth functioning. In the participants' words: while in BiH '*it is matter of bare survival*' (Female, SRJ, Sept 2020), in ST '*it is matter of better, not greater, opportunities*' (Female, BZ, Oct 2019).

¹⁰ these correspond to the *ethnic objectors* once very active in ST while nowadays 'almost non-existent';

4 - Who does Represent the 'Others'?

4.1 Beyond the Greens

Regardless of their ethno-linguistic belonging and/or ideological orientation, the political representatives interviewed in ST acknowledged that the issue of 'Others' is a growing reality. As they explained, the issue is nowadays more complex than in the past, it concerns a wider group of people than the '*traditional linguistically mixed*', and the socio-political implications are more complicated. From a broader perspective, in fact, that of 'Others' is an issue concerning: i) the nature and depth of social divisions drawn upon ethno-linguistic lines; ii) chances, spaces, and possibilities of encounter and dialogue between the various communities (and, by extension, the effective multi/bilingualism of the population); and now more than ever iii) the increased presence of people with foreign backgrounds and/or coming from abroad, not necessarily migrants.

When it comes to the political representation of citizens potentially 'Others', the empirical material collected confirmed the multi-ethnic Greens as the political party closest to and most consistently tackling the issue in its broader sense. The only other party mentioned as progressively 'opening' towards any citizens beyond their ethno-linguistic origins was the Italian Democratic Party (PD). Despite the increased heterogeneity characterising ST society, hence the growing presence of citizens potentially 'Others', its political landscape hardly seems to be adapting, remaining ethno-linguistically polarised (as mostly happens in ethnically divided societies, where the ethnic parties target and represent *only* their own ethnic group's members). For their part, the citizens asked acknowledged and lamented the great responsibility politicians have in addressing the 'issue of 'Others' especially in times of social change.

Since the late 1990s, the interest of politicians in the topic has progressively declined, demonstrating a 'lack of will in going to the very heart of the matter' - paraphrasing what most interviewees said. While important reforms and changes have been made, most agreed that the ST system and its mechanisms still need to be adjusted to the growing heterogeneity characterising present-day society. For this purpose, many mentioned the urgent - though neglected by politics - need to officially count the linguistically mixed persons (*mistilingue*) and mixed families, still compelled to choose between one or another group if they want to participate in the system. As one woman said: *there are a lot of us, I believe at least 60-70% of the total number of families in Bolzano* (Female, BZ, Nov 2019). Nonetheless, political debates concerning Others, their inclusion and representation, are avoided and neglected, and so are those openly questioning the Province's consociational functioning.

We no longer talk about 'Others'. The reality is no longer Italian, German, Ladin but much more complex, and we can't keep adding labels. We must go beyond - beyond stereotypes, groups, narratives according to which 'we must protect ourselves', beyond the 'us and them'. Lots of young people study abroad, many don't come back. We must overcome the past and its limits. The proportional system is an understandable tool but, nowadays, it is old, reductive of the social complexity. We shall move to a system grounded on linguistic competencies, not on ethnic belonging. The social change is happening, migration flows are a challenge, a potential social enrichment. The break will happen naturally, even if the institutions are turning a blind eye. (Female, BZ, Dec 2019)

The respondents - political representatives included - recognised that the core reason why such an important issue is, at the same time, so cautiously marginalised, lies in the very equilibrium and smooth functioning the Autonomous Province has reached over time *thanks* to the very same ethnic quota system. *To do something would mean to change this system, but they do not want to do that because it is politically too risky* (Female, BZ, Nov 2019). Accordingly, the South Tyrolean corporate consociation has, ever since its implementation, succeeded in securing and assuring groups equality,

generating wealth, while avoiding disparities and tensions. These achievements have, in turn, generated and consolidated the perception that such a system, although ethnicity-based and 'old-fashioned', has no urgent reason to be changed. It goes that, although acknowledging its obsolescence vis-a-vis the social changes, both citizens and politicians have overall found more incentives in keeping its mechanisms unaltered than in challenging them. By extension, interactions and cooperation between political representatives and citizens, nowadays, are seldom concerned with political representation and institutional inclusion of citizens potentially 'Others'.

4.2 Beyond Ethnicity

Like the political landscape of South Tyrol, also the Bosnian political scenario is ethnically fragmented and polarised, and the major political parties are oriented towards their own, sole, ethnic constituency. Multi-ethnic civic parties such as *Naša Stranka* (NS - Our Party), the Social Democratic Party (SDP - *Socijaldemokratska Partija Bosne i Hercegovine*), and *Demokratska Fronta* (DF - Democratic Front) are active and popular in the FBiH, and figured among those trying not to align with the ethno-political structure, addressing and representing the whole citizenry regardless of origins and belongings (hence, and by extension, 'Others' too). The primary goal of these parties is to foster supra-ethnic feelings of belonging, familiarise the population with democratic values and human rights, teaching them good practices of active citizenship, while assuring everybody's inclusion and participation. On this subject, it is worth mentioning that, thanks to Naša Stranka's commitment to representing and including *all* Bosnian Herzegovinian citizens within the public bodies and institutions, Canton Sarajevo is now the only one (among the 10 constituting the FBiH¹¹) in which, next to the three Constituent Peoples, 'Others' have also been granted a seat. Overall, civic multi-ethnic parties pursue their goals by trying to engage as much as possible the (largely apathetic) population: as the interviewees explained, they do so by implementing a set of activities ranging from debates and public speeches to door-to-door self-promotion.

Rather different is, instead, the scenario characterising the Republika Srpska (RS), the Entity with a Serbian majority. As the interviewees from Banja Luka (capital city of the RS) acknowledged, in their Entity there is no political party expressly aimed at representing citizens beyond ethnicity and, generally, multi-ethnic civic political parties do not (have any reason to) exist. The most obvious reason seems to be the ethnic composition of the Entity itself, as Bosnian Serbs constitute almost the entirety of the RS's population. Nevertheless, as an MP from the ruling party explained, the SNSD (*Savez nezavisnih socijaldemokrata - Alliance of Independent Social Democrats*) seeks to be a political option for anybody [where] 'Others, as well as people from other communities, are included and can express themselves. [...] We are not exclusivist and we are not nationalist: SNSD is for preserving the RS' autonomy and the interests of all citizens living in its territory (Male, BL, Sept 2020).

Despite its ethnic composition, the RS brings with it a 'peculiar heritage' - which is the reason why, in the course of the 2000s and under the auspices of the international community, a number of constitutional changes were ruled out in order to prevent/avoid ethnicity-based institutional discrimination. The *Council of National Minorities* was created with the purpose of representing and including all those non-Serb citizens whose voices would otherwise not have been heard. The Council has an advisory role in matters of inclusion, inter-ethnic dialogue, and cooperation, and works closely with the National Assembly as well as with the civil society sector. By so doing, 'the Council establishes a direct communication channel with ordinary citizens, as we seek to represent and protect them as best as possible' (Female, BL, Sept 2020).

5 - What Role does the Civil Society Play?

5.1 Adjusting the Aim

From a temporal perspective, the interviewees engaged in local NGOs in the territory of South Tyrol made clear how the politico-institutional developments concerning the 'Others' went hand in hand with the role and activities of civil society; and how, once the 'issue' stopped being (perceived) as such, the civil society organizations had to 'adjust their aim', partly changing their focus and activities. As a person involved in the 1990s' debates and legal fight stated: *in 1991 the 'Others' category was introduced and people thought the problem was solved. [...] With this provision, Langer's battle was losing terrain, and that became clear with the 1991 census [...] Therefore, also our association changed both its name and focus, [...] and began to fight for bilingualism and cooperation. It was a cultural transformation.* (Male, ME, Nov 2019).

Once a less discriminating/more inclusive system was achieved in the 2000s, that of 'Others' progressively started to be perceived as an 'archived', 'solved' issue. Yet: *it only appears to be solved, as the 'issue of Others' actually still persists, and the 2005 new regulation has only further complicated things, introducing the false freedom of the declaration - meaning that, yes, you are allowed to change or modify your declaration, but you are going to pay the consequences. On the one hand, there are many benefits while, on the other one, there also are penalties - which is the reason why nobody dares to do or change anything, it would be totally pointless* (Male, ME, Nov 2019).

The structural changes mentioned produced three main consequences:

i) they reshaped the aims and role the local NGOs working for the 'Others' played until that moment. If up until the 1990s, their role was one of intermediation between the citizens' requests and needs (especially those of linguistically mixed persons) and the political-institutional sphere, from the mid-2000 onwards, it became less political(ly imbued) and gained more of a socio-cultural relevance, aiming less at institutional and more at socio-cultural changes. On this topic, the activists interviewed explained that, among the culturally relevant initiatives they nowadays propose are debates, exhibitions, movies or documentary screenings, book presentations, etc. These initiatives tackle a wide range of themes and issues, yet oftentimes are linked to the specific and peculiar history of South Tyrol, its people and traditions. For this reason, the activities proposed are mostly offered on a bilingual platform, and directed to the broader ST population. Nonetheless, those actually participating belong to a smaller segment of the population: they are often, though not necessarily, linguistically mixed persons or 'Others'; belong to the wealthiest strata of the population; are better educated; are used to travelling and having work/study experiences abroad;

ii) they drastically decreased the political attention given to the 'issue of 'Others''. As the activists interviewed confirmed, while being 'Others' has nowadays become 'the new normality', little attention is given to the same, and the topic is tackled in a 'softer and lighter' way compared to the past. Consequently, the interactions and collaborations between local NGOs dealing with 'beyond-ethnic inclusion and representation' and the political parties have also diminished, further cementing also in the population the belief that the 'issue of 'Others' pertains to the past. When cooperation with the political parties occurs, it is mostly with 'the traditional interlocutor' represented by the Greens - the political party historically more concerned about 'Others'. Yet, depending on the 'social weight' 'Others' have in a specific city/territory, as well as their ethno-linguistic composition, proficient cooperation has also been established between local NGOs and the Italian PD, as well as the South Tyrolean People's Party (SVP) representing German and Ladin speakers;

iii) last but not least, structural changes that took place in the 2000s also modified interactions between civil society and citizens - who, for their part, have progressively learnt how to

¹¹ the Federation of BiH is internally divided into 10 cantons, administrative units similar to Italian regions;

circumnavigate the ethnic divide, aligning with it in order to enjoy an adequate degree of inclusion, representation, and participation. While on the one hand, citizens have mostly become 'self-sufficient', no longer in need of civil society's intermediation; on the other, a feeling of 'abandonment' mirrored in the belief that *'the civil society is basically absent, and people do what they can and by themselves'* (Female, BZ, Nov 2019) became more pronounced especially among the traditional *linguistically mixed*. As many respondents acknowledged when discussing the 'blurred condition' affecting a growing number of ST citizens, oftentimes *'it is the families, the citizens themselves who are self-organising and finding self-made solutions to satisfy their needs. Not the institutions, not the political representatives, and not even civil society'* (Female, BZ, Dec 2019). That feeling of abandonment was often coupled with one of frustration stemming from the evidence that: *everything is divided, nothing is inter-ethnic. Every association is funded by its own councillor, hence also the institutional world is and remains mono-ethnic. And so are both society and politics.* (Female, ME, Mar 2020). To a certain extent, therefore, despite their commitment and aims, the NGOs working on inclusion, inter- and beyond-ethnic dialogue also find themselves in a somehow paradoxical position - compelled, in one way or another, to conform to the ethnic governance they seek to overcome, in turn making the 'Others issue' less urgent, less evident, a 'non-issue'.

5.2 Attention Flows where Money goes

In Bosnia Herzegovina the civil society sector developed consistency in the aftermath of the war. Mostly thanks to support from foreign donors, NGOs *'popped up like mushrooms all over the country'* but, according to the activists interviewed, those *'really active and doing a good job are only a few'* (Female, SRJ, Oct 2020). From a temporal perspective, until about a decade ago 'Others' represented a central topic addressed by the civil society organizations - which, while working on reconciliation, inter-group dialogue, and fighting against ethno-religious discrimination, were also tackling the discrimination entrenched in the DPA provisions. Yet the issue of 'Others' and their ethnic and ethno-territorial discrimination gained wider, even international, attention after the 2008 Sejdić-Finci vs. BiH case - when the representatives of the Roma and Jewish communities, forbidden to run for the Bosnian tripartite Presidency as they were not members of any constituent people, sued the state of BiH and won before the Strasbourg Court of Human Rights. Given the problem was (and still is) inherently constitutional, worthy of mention is the work the many organisations of lawyers present all over Bosnia Herzegovina have done thus far. Yet, in spite of their efforts and proposals, the Bosnian ruling political class has not shown any will to seriously address the issue or change the Bosnian constitution and institutions in a more inclusive and less discriminative way, thus leaving 'Others' in a constant 'blurred condition'.

In the year 2012-13, just before the first post-war census of the population (held in 2013), the civil society sector spent a considerable amount of time and energy in raising awareness among the Bosnian population about the importance of *'declaring how you feel, not what they say you are, not to be afraid of overcoming ethno-national labelling during the population counting'* (Male, BL, Sept 2020). Yet, and once again, despite the many efforts aimed at familiarising the population with the notion of citizenship, shedding light on the many and dangerous consequences of ethnic-identity politics, only 3,7%¹² of the total Bosnian population eventually declared 'Others' during the census. Therefore, while judicial cases similar to the Sejdić-Finci one kept increasing, by 2013 it became clear that the 'issue of 'Others' had lost its relevance and 'urgency', leaving space to new, but old, problems and concerns. As happened in ST, therefore, also the Bosnian civil society organisations had to slightly adapt to the circumstances, shifting their prime attention: *if until 2010-12 there was some hope of institutional and constitutional reforms, now we have totally lost it. [...] also the NGOs and civil society sector have re-directed their efforts and changed the focus: once it was about reconciliation and dialogue, building shared identities, strengthening citizenship. Now it is more on LGBT+ rights, or fighting against corruption* (Female, SRJ, Dic 2200).

A further reason, though connected to the above, for civil society's shift of focus evidenced by the respondents was linked to foreign donors' interests: *nowadays only a few organisations specifically have projects and activities for those who are not part of one of the three groups [...] but much depends on the donors, what issues interest them, which projects they are willing to finance* (Male, MO, Nov 2020). The Bosnian NGOs are, in fact, strictly dependent on foreign donations and funding which, unfortunately, concurred to make the whole civil society sector *'another employment sector. They need donors' money to secure the staff salaries. Very similar projects, if not the very same, are being implemented over and over, since the war's end, and no serious change has been following'* (Female, BL, Oct 2020). According to some, in fact: *many projects are carried out only to receive funding and secure jobs and salaries, without really helping the population they are addressing* (Male, MO, Oct 2020).

Concerning the NGOs' relations and possible cooperation with official politics, the activists from Sarajevo, Mostar and Banja Luka stated that they mostly prefer not to be involved, affiliated or associated with any party, party ideology, or politician of their country. As already mentioned, in fact, the political class in Bosnia Herzegovina is largely corrupt and ethno-nationalist, electorally supported for opportunistic reasons though largely despised. On the other hand, however, the activists also acknowledged that, in the vast majority of the cases, *'the world of politics is not interested in the NGOs' work, they do not consider our projects and results as evidence for change. It is two parallel lines'* (Female, MO, Oct 2020).

Diametrically different, instead, is the kind of relation and bond the NGOs try to build with the population, definitely a closer and stronger one. As the participants overwhelmingly agreed, the civil society organisations aim to act as 'pro-active informants', teaching citizens democracy and its values in order to provide them with the information and tools necessary for their own empowerment, in other words those needed in order to become active citizens aware of their democratic rights and duties. The activities promoted to engage the (mostly apathetic) population include public debates, street protests, door-to-door promotion, as well as summer camps, weekend activities and movie screening to target the younger generations. Social media have been mentioned as a decisive tool used to capture the attention of most strata of the population, allowing both younger and older generations to be reached. Accordingly, *'while the seniors use more WhatsApp, Viber and Facebook, the young are now migrating to other platforms, and we are keeping pace so as to reach them better'* (Male, SRJ, Oct 2020).

¹² Census of population, households and dwellings in Bosnia and Herzegovina - 2013 Final results, Sarajevo 2016;

6 - 'Others' and the City

Can we retrace any similarity or difference concerning 'Others'- their inclusion and representation, and how the issue is framed and perceived - in cities featuring different ethnic compositions? In order to answer such a question, for each case study three urban centres characterised by different ethnic composition were surveyed¹³. In South Tyrol: Bolzano/Bozen, Merano/Meran, and Brunico/Bruneck; in BiH, Sarajevo, Mostar, and Banja Luka. Before proceeding with a territorial investigation about Others, it is worth stressing that, when dealing with consociational and ethnically divided societies, we have to bear in mind that:

- i) the way in which the different groups are located within the territory of their states plays a major role in shaping both their subjective feelings of belonging, and thus modalities of self-identification, and the demand and supply of political and institutional representation and inclusion alike;
- ii) any discourse about collective and individual identities, self-identification, and feelings of belonging, is the outcome of a multitude of variables - including, among others, collective memories, fears, and frustrations; inter-group social and political dynamics and relations; institutional assets and mechanisms; political interests; socio-economic benefits and prestige; and personal experiences and motivations.

The empirical material collected in South Tyrol has not highlighted any significant territorial differences concerning how the discourse of 'Others' was articulated and perceived by the different socio-political actors. There was a difference, instead, in the case of Bosnia Herzegovina, where a higher degree of variability characterised the data collected in Sarajevo, Mostar and Banja Luka.

6.1 Bolzano/Bozen, Merano/Meran, Brunico/Bruneck

Social overview: in **Brunico/Bruneck**, where the German-speaking group is in the majority, the citizens interviewed overall agreed that *'we live much more united than 20 years ago'* (Male, BR, Nov 2019). Although ethno-linguistic divisions have not completely disappeared (particularly when it comes to the more intimate sphere of life), social and political commitment to overcome the boundaries of ethno-linguistic belonging is increasing. A similar perception was shared and highlighted by the younger citizens, who agreed that spaces of inter-ethnic dialogue and encounter are growing, and particularly thanks to civil society initiatives. Nevertheless, given the German group's net majority, the Italians have perfectly assimilated into it; the citizens do not really question their ethno-linguistic identities, and even when they do so, they eventually find their place within the existing categories. In spite of their tradition of coexistence, widespread bilingualism, and absence of an ethnic majority, Italians and Germans in **Merano/Meran** continue living 'next to each other' - as most said. The two groups have traditionally been coexisting in the same urban space yet living parallel lives: *this division is witnessed by the fact that we still do not have as many mixed marriages as we could expect instead* (Male, ME, Oct 2019). The 'Others' mentioned were, in fact, mostly people with a foreign background yet living in the city for decades or more - such as the Russian Orthodox community. The interviewees acknowledged the still present gap between the Italian and German groups, yet depicted a society increasingly committed to shortening that distance and going beyond ethno-linguistic distinctions. Last but not least, the scenario portrayed in the city of **Bolzano/Bozen** was slightly different, as the city was described as 'divided'.

¹³ See Tables in *Introduction*;

In Bolzano, we know that the city center is German, the suburbs are Italian, and we have lots of foreigners coming from Morocco, Tunisia, Bangladesh living in the central area because half of their rent is paid by the municipality. [...] Divisions are between Germans and Italians, nobody cares about the Ladins – it's just folklore (Male, BZ, Nov 2019)

In spite of its divided character, the interviewees largely agreed that it is in Bolzano/Bozen, more than in any other urban center, that individuals potentially falling into the category 'Others' are numerically increasing, becoming 'a new normality'. The phenomenon was linked to a perceived increase in mixed marriages, young 'cosmopolitan' people, as well as an increased presence of individuals with foreign origins and backgrounds.

Political overview: the politicians interviewed in Bolzano/Bozen, Merano/Meran, and Brunico/Bruneck did not acknowledge any recent significant request for greater inclusion, representation or participation. The political representation of 'Others' remains a priority of the Greens party in each city surveyed. Particularly in **Bolzano/Bozen**, the Italian PD is also addressing and seeking to represent the political interests of the growing number of people with foreign backgrounds while, in Brunico/Bruneck, the SVP displayed some serious commitment to include those belonging to ethno-national minorities. Institutionally speaking, ethnic balance and proportionality within all state bodies are a consolidated reality guaranteeing the system's smooth functioning, and the declaration of linguistic belonging/aggregation still guarantees efficiency, allowing virtually anybody to enter and benefit from the system. The only territory-based difference mentioned was the socio-political impact,, which echoed the impact events and debates in the 1980s and 1990s had had on the urban communities - which made the citizens of **Bolzano/Bozen** 'particularly sensitive' about the 'issue of 'Others'. As the respondents acknowledged, this translated into a number of activities and initiatives (particularly though not exclusively concerning the need for multilingual school education); the creation of NGOs specifically addressing the 'Others' needs; as well as a progressive increase in mixed unions and marriages. The topic also had an echo in **Merano/Meran**, while in the smaller city of **Brunico/Bruneck** that of 'Others' has not - despite its relevance - had the same social impact as in the other two urban centres. This however does not mean 'Others' did/do not exist.

Civil society overview: last but not least, in each of the three urban centres there are organizations either set up with the purpose of targeting and addressing 'Others', or which mutated their initial mission to bridge the gap between the ethno-linguistic communities. Among others, worthy of mention are: *Diverkstatt* and *Il Telaio* in **Brunico/Bruneck**, *Ost-West* and *Co-Working della Memoria* in **Merano/Meran**, the 'historical' *Alexander Langer Foundation* in **Bolzano/Bozen**, as well as organisations such as *Mix-Ling*, *Convivia*, and *Athesis* - these latter two no longer operating. These NGOs are all oriented toward the whole population regardless of, or beyond, ethno-linguistic specificities; they try to familiarise the citizens with topics, concepts, and issues of particular relevance for the multiethnic-linguistic territory and its population, proposing debates and public meetings able to foster and nurture critical thinking. Last but not least, it is worth stressing that, sometimes, it is the world of politics and institutions that encourages the creation of forms of cooperation aimed at building greater social cohesion and inclusion. This is the case of the *Consulta Integrazione e Migrazione* (CIM), and the *Consulta Giovani*. These 'quasi institutional' organs, built inside the institutions of the state but composed of ordinary citizens and civil society representatives, have succeeded in establishing themselves as 'alternative' spaces of encounter and dialogue able to bridge and connect social, political and civil society actors, as well as members of the different (domestic and non) ethno-linguistic groups. Their existence and work are therefore crucial in matters of inclusion and representation and, by addressing and involving all citizens, they go beyond ethno-linguistic labels and categories – including that of 'Others'.

6.2 Sarajevo, Mostar, and Banja Luka

Social overview: When discussing 'Others' in the various areas of BiH and especially in the urban centres of **Sarajevo**, **Mostar** and **Banja Luka**, all the participants stressed the enormous gap existing between those cities and their surrounding areas, the villages. A second territorial difference mentioned was between Sarajevo and Banja Luka on the one hand, and Mostar on the other - with the latter lacking a 'critical mass'. Probably also because of its historical heritage, **Sarajevo** is the city considered the most open-minded and liberal, remaining (at least symbolically) the cradle of cosmopolitanism. It is in Sarajevo that we can find a growing number of citizens feeling and declaring 'Others' as a form of political protest and rebellion against the ethno-nationalist, corrupt, political élite. Yet **Banja Luka**, the capital city of Republika Srpska, was very similarly described. Although ethno-national homogeneity offers lower chances of questioning collective and individual identities and self-identifications, the heavily nationalist propaganda characterising the RS seems to incentivise, particularly among the younger generations, the rejection of ethno-national labelling and categorisation. Nevertheless, the question of 'Others' does not really constitute an issue. Concerning **Mostar**, the participants recalled how *once* this city was also a very mixed one, and how various factors then concurred to make it so divided. Although there are still lots of people with mixed backgrounds, when it comes to feeling 'Others' in virtue of their personal experiences and/or political opinions, at the end of the day *'they do not feel safe to declare they are Others, and to vote for non-nationalist parties, because it is like betraying your own group; giving the other group room "to invade" your space'* (Female, MO, Dic 2020).

Political overview: also from a political perspective, the dominant political parties in **Mostar** are the ones representing the two bigger groups (Bosniaks and Bosnian Croats). Until recently, the multi-ethnic civil society party *Naša Stranka* was the only one trying to counterbalance the ethno-nationalist oligarchs, yet since 2018 *Platform za Progress (Platform for Progress)* has also been active and fighting against ethno-nationalism. A different political scenario characterises **Banja Luka**. The RS political parties generally only represent/address the Bosnian Serb population – who account for 90% of the Entity's total population. Most respondents, in fact, pointed out the total absence of non-Serb political parties, as well as political discourse aiming at greater inclusion. Multi/non-ethnic parties similar to those active in the FBiH do not exist; nor have the multi/non-ethnic parties based in the FBiH succeeded in establishing their branches in the RS. Accordingly, demands for greater inclusion and participation, at both political and institutional level, have largely been a concern of the FBiH, hence addressed and channelled by parties such as the Social Democrats (SDP), *Demokratska Fronta*, or the **Sarajevo**-based *Naša Stranka* – created in 2008 on civil society initiative.

Civil society overview: in the light of its peculiar past, the civil society sector of BiH is rather young and not very experienced; yet, especially thanks to foreign donations and support, it has consistently grown - though mostly in Sarajevo and Banja Luka, where most of the financial help has been directed. Among others, the **Sarajevo** based NGO *Zašto ne?* (Why not?) has been doing a great job ever since its creation in the aftermath of the war, and notably in the year prior to the 2013 census and across the 2013-14 wave of protests. Many other civil society organisations such as, for instance, *Humanity in Action*, run projects on democratisation and active citizenship, targeting especially the younger generation, and aim to familiarise and teach (young) citizens about the complexities of the Bosnian system and society, as well as the discrimination and injustices intrinsic to the Bosnian constitutional and institutional set-up. In **Banja Luka** worthy of mention is BASOC, an acronym for 'Banja Luka SOcial Center'. Created in 2015 with the aim of giving people an ethnically and politically neutral space where they can express themselves, BASOC works on memory politics, social justice, and feminism. It *'does not compromise with official politics or with foreign donors, we want to be independent and not to accept compromises'* (Male, Banja Luka, Nov 2020) - said one of its leaders. Similarly, the activities proposed by *Oštra Nula* (Sharp Zero) and other NGOs also target the whole citizenry, and the many activities proposed seek to familiarise citizens with democratic values and active citizenship. Yet it is mostly the young people that attend and participate in such events and activities. Lastly, the civil society of **Mostar** is instead largely committed to bridging the gap between

the two communities, and a considerable amount of resources has been allocated to projects in the field of school education. On this subject, the work of NGOs such as *Nansen Dialogue* happen to be of particular relevance. Nonetheless, the civil society sector in Mostar has been described as ‘*underdeveloped, non-existent*’ (Female, Mostar, Sept 2020) because most foreign donations have been, and still are, directed towards Sarajevo and Banja Luka, as well as because of ‘*people’s conformist mentality and lack of critical thinking*’ (Female, BL, Oct 2020).

7- Perspectives on the Future

7.1 South Tyrol: Obsolescence vs Efficiency

The vast majority of the participants, regardless of their ethno-linguistic belonging, institutional role, or city of origin, agreed that: *the ethnic proportional system is obsolete but provides job positions and makes society work smoothly...yet it also renders the Province provincial. The system is old but it works: it keeps everything inside and guarantees the garden will always be tidy and produce juicy apples. Here we live really well, why should we ever change?! (Male, BZ, Nov 2019).* And again: *there is no change, and you know why? Because we are too comfortable. Economic wealth plays a huge role in pushing for social, political, and institutional change. Everybody here has a good life, nobody is willing to change that. Why dismantle a system that is producing and guaranteeing wealth for everybody? (Female, BR, Jan 2020).*

Consociationalism and ethnic power-sharing mechanisms have often been described as discriminatory, ethnically exclusive, obsolete, reductive, inadequate to bring about social change. Nevertheless, and at the same time, they have been acknowledged as being only *apparently* rigid, thus potentially inclusive, given the possibilities of circumnavigating ‘ethnic obstacles’. Accordingly, although in principle recognising the need for institutional change, most interviewees eventually acknowledged that the (f)actual flexibility of an apparently rigid system, further incentivises both citizens and political representatives to go along with it, to align with the ethnic governance while benefitting from the opportunities granted to everybody - on the sole condition of alignment. *We keep on living this way until events themselves impose a change. We have become pragmatic, we save time and effort, we do not argue, and it is ok like this (Male, BR, Mar 2020).*

As most of the politicians interviewed agreed, institutional change in a more inclusive direction does necessarily represent ‘the next step’. Nevertheless, how to get there is still unclear. The creation of a fourth - ‘Others’ - category and its inclusion in the quota system has unanimously been rejected, as it would only further ‘pillarise’ the system. The temporary suspension of the quota system in favour of merit- and need-driven criteria (already happening, though occasionally and not officially) has also been rejected. Political reluctance to ‘touch’ the proportional system stems from the fact that, as it stands, ethnic power-sharing not only represents an indispensable organisational tool, the basis for the Province’s actual Autonomy, but - and perhaps even more importantly - it serves psychological functions, representing the necessary safety net safeguarding a group’s identity, status, and power alike. Accordingly, the overcoming of ethno-linguistic affiliations, and the creation of a supra-ethnic identity, is not and has never been a goal pursued by the political actors - *‘the melting pot is not a desirable solution and outcome [and] a certain degree of separation has to be kept in place’ (Male, BZ, Jan 2020)* in order to justify - over and over again - both the Autonomy’s very existence and survival, and its mechanisms of (ethno-)political representation and distribution of resources.

At the end of the day, in fact, both the ethnic quotas and the declaration of linguistic belonging/aggregation have represented one of the mechanisms upon which the whole idea and functioning of the South Tyrolean autonomy is built, and it is in virtue of these ‘apparently rigid’ mechanisms that peace - though negative (Carlà 2018) - has been reached and can be preserved.

7.2 (Re)empowering the City in Bosnia Herzegovina

In Bosnia Herzegovina the problems intrinsic to the ethnic power-sharing mechanisms are slightly more difficult to overcome: the most urgent and concerning of all seems to be those of corruption and clientelism, largely working on ethnic bases and through ethno-national party affiliation. Overcoming ethno-national affiliations by (re)creating a shared sense of belonging to the country of BiH is a desirable though largely unrealistic option: *that was a goal to be pursued in the first decade after the end of the war (Male, SRJ, Sept 2020).*

A more realistic, and urgent, goal to be achieved is constitutional reform, '*not a compromise, but a change to allow anybody to participate*' (Female, MO, Oct 2020): in fact, not only 'Others' are discriminated by virtue of the ethnic mechanisms of representation and participation, but injustices are also being perpetrated on an ethno-territorial base. Yet, as in ST, upgrading 'Others' to the status of (fourth) Constituent People within the existing ethnic power-sharing framework is seen by many as pointless and problematic. Although some are advocating, like in ST, a slow and progressive abandoning of the quota system in favour of merit-driven criteria, a more realistic analysis of the situation requires different, alternative solutions.

In the light of the high level of decentralisation characterising the FBiH, the solution envisaged by most is the empowering of the local dimension, rendering the city and its inhabitants the key factors of change. By becoming laboratories of active citizenship through the re-appropriation of shared spaces, the cultivation of a sense of belonging to the same urban community - beyond, and regardless of ethnicity - the city and the municipality level aim to become positive examples of democratic participation. This is the goal that most local branches of multi-ethnic and civic parties, as well as local NGOs, are actually pursuing. They aim to show to the whole population that *there is* an alternative to ethnocracy, that another way of participating into the country's public life is possible. By extension, the focus on the local, municipality level fosters synergies between the politico-institutional sphere - rendering it more accountable - and the citizenry, encouraged to actively participate and cooperate, also for the common good.

Conclusion

The empirical material collected in South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina through semi-structured interviews performed between 2019 and 2020, has overall shown that 'Others'- be them from ethnically mixed backgrounds, minority groups not specifically included in the power-sharing mechanism, or citizens rejecting ethnic categorisation - largely remain 'invisible' and neglected in both the scenarios surveyed. In spite of a few differences, in both South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina, citizens, and particularly those potentially '*Others*', have strong incentives to align themselves with the ethnic governance in which they live. Even when described as 'obsolete' and 'rigid' - as in South Tyrol, or an 'ethnocracy' - as in BiH, ethnic alignment seems to be the option most practised in order to enjoy the benefits of - as in ST, or to survive - as in Bosnia, the ethnic power-sharing system.

Therefore, while all those belonging to none or more than one of the major societal segments, or irresolute with regard to the question, may feel discriminated against or excluded in virtue of their formal exclusion, it is also true they are allowed and even encouraged by the system to align with the ethnic divide, choosing suboptimal collective identities in order to take advantage of the opportunities offered by the consociational ethnic mechanisms. By so doing, they at the same time concur to safeguard the systems' functioning in the very name of pragmatism and opportunism.

At first glance it thus seems that the category 'Others' is destined to disappear - as those potentially falling into it seem to be furnished with good enough reasons to align with the ethnic governance, to use ethnic collective identities as proxies to enter the system, thereby benefitting from it while leaving it unchanged.

According to the hypotheses initially formulated, the research findings show that:

Hp 1) in both consociations, 'Others' have learnt how to carve out their own spaces and satisfy their needs, and they do so mostly by aligning with pre-determined categories;

Hp 2) 'opportunistic alignment' is the most practised strategy - yet while in ST there is a 'winning group', in BiH people's alignment follows both ethno-territorial and informal criteria (mostly favouritism and clientelism);

Hp 3) in ST, contrary to what was expected, neither those coming from mixed marriages, the younger 'cosmopolitan and multilingual' generations, nor the 'new minorities' seem to be asking for a change in the system that would grant greater inclusion and representation. Although expected to feel 'uncomfortable' with the ethno-linguistic categorisation, hence more critical, active and vocal, those potentially 'Others' largely go along with the status quo. In BiH the scenario that emerged was no different, with the only - though meaningful exception - of the '*Others* against': a critical mass of citizens, growing especially in the major urban centres, and generally participating in the political and social life of the country in order to bring about change and overcome the boundaries of ethnic belonging;

Hp 4) only in the case of BiH, the younger generations, although emotionally and temporarily detached from the conflict/ethnic tensions, happened to be less inclined to adapt to the system, interact and/or engage (slightly) more with civil society and civic multi-ethnic parties alike. In ST, instead, although *when asked* they sounded rather critical towards the ST 'ethnic-mechanisms', the younger generations neither problematised their ethno-linguistic belonging or modalities of self-identification, nor were they concerned about the potential discrimination intrinsic to the ethnic proportional system. Hence, they seldom engage in politics or interact with civil society with the specific purpose of gaining greater inclusion and representation;

Hp 5) as expected, in BiH, civil society more consistently interacts with the citizens but not with the world of politics. More than an intermediary, Bosnian civil society seeks to play the role of 'pro-active informant', providing citizens with the tools necessary for their own empowerment. In ST, instead, civil society's role as intermediary between the needs and demands of citizens 'Others' on the one hand, and politics and institutions on the other, is something pertaining to the past. The ST civil society has, in the last fifteen years, readjusted its aims, and its role is less politically imbued and more of socio-cultural relevance;

Hp 6) as expected, in ST both the multi-ethnic political party(ies) and civil society seek change that goes *beyond* ethno-linguistic distinctions. Yet, the achievement of that goal is no longer a priority, and the whole 'issue of 'Others' has lost its urgency. In BiH, greater ('Others') inclusion and participation represent the main goals pursued by the multi-ethnic parties, yet the topic is far from being at the top of the country's political agenda. Concerning civil society, also in the Bosnian case we see a change in the goals pursued - overall a shift towards more urgent (i.e. corruption) and donor-driven topics and interests (i.e. LGBT+ community rights);

Hp 7) as expected, due to stability reasons, the 'issue of 'Others' has progressively lost its relevance and urgency, from both political-institutional and social perspectives. In both consociations surveyed, although that of 'Others' remains 'a reality', the various social and political actors have found more incentives in going along with the current system and divisions than fighting against them. From a real-life perspective, in fact, that of 'Others' represents a growing reality both in ST (as mixed unions are said to be becoming 'normal', growing in number) and in BiH (as those rejecting ethnic labelling are increasing, especially in the bigger cities). Yet, on the other hand, it is also true that citizens potentially 'Others' do largely display a tendency here addressed in terms of 'opportunistic alignment' with the ethnic governance and divide.

To conclude, the research findings make way for two broader reflections, as we might question:

1) *the alleged rigidity of corporate consociations*: the possibility to give 'false' declarations concerning one's own ethno-linguistic belonging, the absence of checks and punishments, as well as the adoption of occasional *ad hoc* solutions as in ST, or the often 'informal and personalised' character of the implementation of quotas as in BiH, allow the corporate consociations to elude rigidity and ethnic exclusivism by potentially including *anybody* on the sole condition of ethnic alignment. As widely emerged in both case studies, and in spite of their reputation as being ethnically exclusive, discriminatory, old fashioned, anachronistic etc, both the South Tyrolean and Bosnia Herzegovinian consociations keep on functioning *as they are*. Not only have both corporate consociations demonstrated to actually be flexible and inclusive but, at the end of the day, they both succeed in satisfying their most important function, which is psychological - making clear that, in the end, the groups composing the plural societies of South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina are still not ready to abandon the safety net provided by ethnic quotas and mechanisms, and that they are better off living *next to each other* though under a common roof;

2) *the 'otherness of 'Others'*: while in ST those potentially 'Others' have been acknowledged to be a growing number of citizens, their alleged growth does not imply that they either actually feel they belong, or declare membership, to the Others category; nor that the category 'Others' is acquiring a new socio-political relevance or requires institutional changes. It goes that, even in those cases of potential 'Otherness', the majority of citizens do not feel 'cut off from the system', and (in recent times) there have no been pressures for greater political representation or institutional inclusion. Similarly, while a growing number of Bosnian Herzegovinian citizens are claiming the right to feel, declare, and be represented as such – in other words belonging to the group of 'Others', the vast majority align and conform to the ethnic scaffolding, paving the way to continuity of both the ethnocratic way of ruling and identity politics, as well as the capturing of the state.

To conclude, the study demonstrates that, although differing mostly on the surface, South Tyrol and Bosnia Herzegovina have much in common when it comes to socio-political dynamics connected with and partly triggered by their peculiar institutional design. Although due to different reasons, in both consociations individual bearers of identities not included and foreseen by the system are largely incentivised to align with the ethnic governance and divide - and eventually they do so. What has been addressed here in terms of 'opportunistic alignment' emerged to be the most commonly practised strategy adopted to face and overcome the potential exclusion caused by (apparently) rigid and ethnicity-based mechanisms of institutional inclusion and political representation.

'Others' emerge as key actors in stabilising and legitimising ethnic-based consociations and systems via opportunistic alignment, as they concur to: i) disenfranchise both the political actors and civil society working for 'beyond ethnic' inclusion and representation, concurring to make the issue of 'Others' less urgent, thus marginal; and ii) progressively decrease the social and political need for the very existence of the category '*Others*', as the needs and interests of its potential members are much better satisfied when they conform to the ethnic divide. Citizens 'Others', therefore, are far from being marginal actors, as they play the key role of maintaining in place 'apparently exclusive and rigid systems' by aligning with - and thus legitimising - the ethnic governance and divide.

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